

Types and Causes of Disasters in University Libraries: Evidence from North East Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the types and causes of disasters affecting university libraries in North East Nigeria. University libraries play a critical role in supporting teaching, learning, research, and knowledge preservation, yet they remain vulnerable to disasters that threaten collections, infrastructure, ICT facilities, and service continuity. The study addressed the limited empirical documentation of disaster experiences in university libraries within the region. Guided by two research questions, the study adopted a qualitative research approach within a constructivist paradigm and employed a multiple-case study design. The population comprised thirteen university librarians in public universities in North East Nigeria, selected through total population purposive sampling. Data were collected through in-depth, face-to-face key informant interviews using a semi-structured interview guide, while thematic analysis was conducted with the aid of ATLAS.ti software. Findings revealed that university libraries in the region had experienced disasters such as electrical faults, electrical sparks, fire incidents, windstorms, roof leakages, flooding, erosion, and structural cracks. The causes of these disasters were linked to environmental factors, including rainstorms, floods, windstorms, erosion, and soil expansion; human-induced factors, such as carelessness, wrong electrical connections, delayed maintenance responses, and bureaucratic protocols; and technological factors, including power surges, equipment failure, and faulty wiring. The study concluded that disasters in university libraries are products of interconnected environmental, infrastructural, human, and technological vulnerabilities across affected institutions. It recommended increased funding, periodic risk assessment, improved infrastructure, geotechnical assessment in erosion-prone areas, and stronger institutional disaster prevention and response systems.

Keywords: *Disaster management; University libraries; Risk assessment; Library safety; Fire prevention; Digital preservation; Nigeria*

Introduction

Disasters have become an increasingly prominent feature of contemporary societies, affecting not only human lives and economic systems but also institutional infrastructures that support knowledge creation and dissemination. Globally, the frequency and intensity of both natural and human-induced disasters have risen over the past decades, resulting in widespread destruction of physical assets and disruption of essential services. These events are often sudden, unpredictable, and capable of overwhelming the coping capacity of affected organisations, particularly in developing regions where infrastructural and environmental vulnerabilities are pronounced.

Disaster is commonly defined as a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or organisation that causes significant human, material, environmental, or economic losses exceeding the ability of the affected entity to respond using its own resources (United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction [UNISDR], 2017). Disasters may arise from natural phenomena such as floods, storms, fires, and extreme weather conditions, or from human activities including conflict, vandalism, infrastructural failures, and technological breakdowns. In institutional settings, these events often expose latent weaknesses in physical structures, operational systems, and risk management practices.

University libraries, as central components of academic institutions, are particularly vulnerable to disasters due to the nature of their collections, infrastructure, and service delivery systems. Libraries house vast quantities of print and non-print resources, digital collections, archival materials, and technological equipment that are highly susceptible to damage from fire, water, biological agents, and human interference. A library disaster may be understood as any event that disrupts the normal functioning of the library, prevents access to information resources, or results in damage or loss of collections and facilities. Feather and Matthews (2003) observed that libraries are inherently vulnerable to disasters because many threats occur without warning and can rapidly render records and documents inaccessible or permanently destroyed.

Evidence from different parts of the world indicates that libraries are frequently affected by a wide range of disasters, including fire outbreaks, flooding, vandalism, pest infestation, electrical faults, and acts of violence associated with social unrest and terrorism (Davou, 2016; Gupta, Starr, Farahani, & Matinrad, 2016). In tropical regions such as sub-Saharan Africa, environmental conditions further exacerbate the risk of damage, as high humidity, extreme temperatures, and biological agents such as insects and rodents accelerate the deterioration of library materials. These hazards pose serious threats to the preservation of intellectual heritage and the continuity of academic services.

In North East Nigeria, the disaster risk landscape is shaped by a complex interaction of environmental, infrastructural, and security-related factors. The region has experienced recurring environmental hazards alongside heightened levels of insecurity, vandalism, and insurgency-related disruptions, all of which have implications for public institutions, including university libraries. Disasters affecting libraries in this context often result in extensive damage to collections, destruction of ICT infrastructure, interruption of services, and loss of irreplaceable academic and

research materials. Such occurrence affects the core mission of university libraries to support teaching, learning, and research.

Understanding the types of disasters and their underlying causes in university libraries is therefore critical for developing evidence-based strategies aimed at reducing losses and strengthening institutional resilience. However, meaningful interventions require empirical knowledge of the specific disaster experiences of libraries within particular contexts. This study contributes to this need by examining the types and causes of disasters affecting university libraries in North East Nigeria, thereby providing context-specific insights into the vulnerabilities of academic information institutions in disaster-prone environments.

Statement of the Problem

University libraries are essential to the academic enterprise, serving as custodians of knowledge resources and as hubs for teaching, learning, and research activities. Despite their importance, these libraries remain highly susceptible to a variety of disasters that threaten their collections, infrastructure, and service delivery. Globally, numerous studies have documented the vulnerability of libraries to natural and human-induced disasters; however, the specific patterns and causes of such disasters vary significantly across regions and institutional contexts. In North East Nigeria, university libraries operate within an environment characterised by environmental hazards, infrastructural deficiencies, biological threats, and security challenges. Reports of fire outbreaks, flooding, vandalism, pest infestations, theft, and damage arising from conflict-related activities suggest that disasters constitute a persistent threat to the sustainability of library services in the region. These incidents often result in the loss of print and electronic resources, destruction of ICT facilities, disruption of academic services, and long-term setbacks to research and knowledge preservation. Yet, despite the severity of these impacts, systematic documentation of the types and causes of disasters affecting university libraries in the region remains limited.

The absence of detailed empirical evidence on the disaster experiences of university libraries in North East Nigeria creates a significant knowledge gap. Without a clear understanding of the specific disasters encountered, their root causes, it becomes difficult for stakeholders to appreciate the scale of the problem or to design targeted interventions. Moreover, existing discussions on disaster management in libraries in Nigeria have often focused on preparedness and policy issues, with insufficient attention paid to the actual disaster events and their tangible effects on library operations and resources.

This lack of context-specific evidence underscores the need for a focused investigation into the types and causes of disasters affecting university libraries in North East Nigeria. Addressing this gap is essential for informing institutional planning, guiding resource allocation, and strengthening awareness of disaster risks within academic library environments. Consequently, this study seeks to provide empirical insights into the disaster landscape of university libraries in the region by systematically examining the nature of disasters experienced, the factors that give rise to them, and their implications for library collections, infrastructure, and service continuity.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What types of disasters have occurred in university libraries in North East Nigeria?
2. What are the causes of disasters in university libraries in North East Nigeria?

Literature Review

Types of Disasters in University Libraries

University libraries are critical knowledge repositories that support teaching, learning, and research. Despite their importance, they are highly vulnerable to various forms of disasters that can disrupt services and lead to significant loss of resources. Disasters in libraries are generally categorized into natural, human-induced, and technological types. Natural disasters such as floods, storms, and extreme weather conditions have been widely reported as major threats to library collections and infrastructure. These events often result in water damage, structural failures, and deterioration of materials, particularly in regions with high rainfall and humidity. According to the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (2019), flooding remains one of the most destructive hazards affecting institutions globally, especially in areas with inadequate drainage systems.

Human-induced disasters, including vandalism, theft, negligence, and conflict-related destruction, also pose serious risks to libraries. Akussah and Bentil (2010) found that misuse and deliberate damage to library materials significantly affect access to information resources in academic institutions. In regions affected by insecurity, libraries may also experience damage from acts of violence and civil unrest. Technological disasters have become increasingly significant with the growing reliance on digital systems in libraries. Power outages, system failures, and data loss can disrupt access to digital resources and compromise information services. Miller and Pellen (2008) noted that failures in electrical and technological systems are among the most common risks faced by modern libraries, particularly in environments with unstable power supply.

Understanding the types of disasters that affect libraries is essential for developing effective disaster preparedness and response strategies. These categories provide a framework for identifying risks and implementing targeted interventions to protect library resources and infrastructure.

Causes of Disasters in University Libraries

Disasters in university libraries are rarely random occurrences; rather, they result from identifiable environmental, infrastructural, human, and technological factors. Understanding these causes is essential for effective disaster prevention and management.

Environmental factors are among the most significant causes of disasters in libraries, particularly in tropical and developing regions. Heavy rainfall, flooding, and extreme weather conditions have been identified as major contributors to structural damage and deterioration of collections. Feather and Matthews (2003) observed that environmental conditions such as humidity and temperature fluctuations accelerate the degradation of library materials and increase vulnerability to biological threats. Infrastructural deficiencies also play a critical role in disaster occurrence. Poor building design, aging structures, faulty electrical systems, and inadequate maintenance practices significantly increase the risk of fire outbreaks, water damage, and structural collapse. Studies have shown that many library disasters are linked to preventable infrastructural failures rather than unavoidable external events (Miller and Pellen, 2008).

Human-related factors, including negligence, lack of awareness, and poor adherence to safety procedures, are frequently cited as major causes of disasters in libraries. Improper handling of electrical equipment, failure to enforce safety regulations, and delays in maintenance responses contribute to increased vulnerability. George (1995) emphasized that lack of preparedness and awareness among staff significantly heightens disaster risks in library environments. Biological factors such as pest infestation and mould growth are also significant causes of damage to library collections, particularly in humid environments. These threats often result from poor environmental control and inadequate sanitation practices, leading to gradual but extensive deterioration of materials (Feather & Matthews, 2003).

Technological factors, including power outages, equipment failure, and inadequate digital backup systems, have emerged as critical causes of disasters in modern libraries. Olanrewaju et al. (2021) highlighted that unstable electricity supply and lack of technological infrastructure significantly affect the sustainability of digital library services in Nigeria. Furthermore, security-related issues such as theft, vandalism, and conflict further contribute to disaster risks in libraries. These factors not only result in loss of materials but also disrupt access to information and reduce user confidence in library services (Akussah & Bentil, 2010). The causes of disasters in university libraries are multifaceted and interconnected. Addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach that integrates environmental management, infrastructural improvement, staff training, and technological investment.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research approach within a constructivist paradigm to explore disaster management practices in university libraries in North East Nigeria. The constructivist worldview assumes that reality is socially constructed and that knowledge is derived from participants' lived experiences and interpretations of their social contexts (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Ngulube, 2019). A multiple-case study design was employed to enable an in-depth examination of disaster-related practices within their real-life institutional settings, allowing for rich contextual understanding (Yin, 2018). The study population comprised heads of public university libraries in North East Nigeria. A total population purposive sampling technique was adopted, involving all thirteen (13) university librarians in the region, as they were considered key informants with direct responsibility for disaster preparedness and management in their respective institutions (Maree, 2016). Data were collected through in-depth, face-to-face key informant

interviews using a semi-structured interview guide. The instrument was validated through expert review and pretested outside the study area to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives (Creswell, 2016). Trustworthiness of the data was ensured through credibility, dependability, and confirmability measures, including prolonged engagement, peer debriefing, and audit trails (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis, following systematic processes of transcription, coding, categorisation, and theme development (Braun & Clarke, 2006). ATLAS.ti software was employed to support data organisation and enhance analytic rigour. Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study, including informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity of respondents.

Results

Research Question One: What types of disasters have occurred in university libraries in North East Nigeria?

To answer research question one on the types of disasters that have occurred in the university libraries of North East Nigeria, the data collected were analysed using ATLAS.ti software and the results revealed that the types of disasters that have occurred in the university libraries in North East Nigeria were electrical faults, electricity sparks, fire incidents, windstorms, leakages on the roof of the building and erosion. This is illustrated graphically in Figure 1

Figure 1: Types of Disasters Encountered in University Libraries

One of the librarians said that:

Yes, the only disaster that I have experienced in the library was a fire incident, windstorms and leakages on the roof of the building. Because of constant leakages, books are sometimes removed and kept aside for safety (Librarian 1).

This result shows that the types of disasters that have occurred in the University Libraries of North East Nigeria are similar. The results show that the types of disasters that have occurred in the University Libraries of North East Nigeria are not peculiar to a specific university. Even though the types of disasters seemed similar, not all university libraries experienced the same disaster. One of the librarians said that:

No, but there was a time when there were leakages on the roof. Water splashed on the table of one of the computers, but the computer is still working perfectly. We have made a backup of the documents on that computer in case of failure of the computer to function as a result of the damage that may occur in the near future as a result of that leakage (Librarian 3).

It was established that not all university libraries in the North East Nigeria have experienced disaster. This was confirmed by one of the participants, who said, "I cannot remember encountering any disaster in my library because we have controlled what would have led to disaster in the library, which is an electrical fault."

This finding aligns with Feather and Matthews (2003), who identified electrical faults as a major cause of library disasters. This finding shows that university libraries in North East Nigeria have encountered one disaster or another. Even though the disasters were not of significant magnitude, they have occurred in one way or the other.

Research Question Two: What are the causes of disasters in university libraries in North East Nigeria?

Research question two examined the causes of disaster in university libraries in North East Nigeria indicated that there are three basic causes of disaster, the first of which is environmental causes such as fire, rainstorm, flood and windstorm, erosion, and land expansion. There are manmade causes such as human error, carelessness, and delays from individuals, delays from the works department and bureaucratic protocol. The third is technological factors such as electricity, electrical sparks, equipment failure, and equipment damage. Other causes of disaster identified were design vulnerability, electricity and electrical sparks, wrong electrical connections, fire incidence, electrical appliances, windstorm, water splash and roof leakages. This is illustrated graphically in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Causes of Disasters in University Libraries

Commonly identified among the causes were electricity and electrical sparks. This disaster was attributed to wrong electrical connections, improper wiring, and the use of inferior materials during wiring. This disaster can be classified as a human-induced disaster because of the failure to use quality materials when wiring the Library.

In specific terms, to each library, participants reported fire incidence caused by electricity and electrical sparks, windstorm blowing up the roof of the building and leakages caused by water. These disasters were common among university libraries, as almost all university libraries have experienced them.

For environmental causes, participants identified fire, rainstorm, flood, windstorm, erosion and land expansion. One of the librarians responded that:

The only disaster that has occurred so far is wind and erosion. The library was built on an erosion line, so there are cracks on the floor and the walls of the library. The land surveyors were invited to come and see the problem, and they explained that this problem is not only in the university alone, but it affects other states, the Republic of Chad and Cameroon. It has started in Cameroon, through Chad, and Nigeria, which has to do with the earthquake. I couldn't really understand what he explained, whether it is on a titanic plate or something. You know, it has to do with a geography thing which brought about the cracks (Librarian 4).

A follow-up question to determine whether the disaster has affected library services in the university, the response was affirmative that it has affected the operational capacity of the library. The librarian said that:

Yes, it has. There is the fear of the building collapsing, so I told my staff that we will not go there, and they have tried to make some repairs on the building. People are afraid to go there because the building is upstairs. When you are climbing the staircase, you hear a sound, so people are afraid that the building will collapse. We are not going to move there. There is a lot of engineering work going on there now. Pillars have been erected, and the construction work is still ongoing at the moment (Librarian 5).

When asked what the cause was, the librarian said that:

The cause of the disaster in the library building, they say it is soil expansion, it is a geography issue. The thing has affected our library. You will notice a crack on the soil which has affected the library building creating crack on the floor and on the building. The State Surveyor General says it starts from the Mediterranean up to the Republic of Chad. It also affected the Polytechnic and many buildings because the library is along the same line, so it affected many states, not only in our university library (Librarian 5).

On manmade causes participants identified human error, carelessness, delays from individuals, delay from works department and bureaucratic protocol. In one of the libraries it was noticed that part of the problem was manmade due to wrong electrical connection. The Librarian noted that:

There were wrong electrical connections that we started noticing before we alerted the works department. We put out all light in the library from the control switch before the works and maintenance department arrived (Librarian 2)

Another librarian reported leaking water from the roof as one of the environmental causes that caused damage to the library. He said that:

..... there was leakages on the roof of the library building. Water splashed on the table of one of the computers but the computer is still working perfectly. We have made a backup of the documents on that computer in cases of failure of the computer to function as a result of the damage that may occur in the near future as a result of that leakage.... (Librarian 1)

Delays in response to calls for repairs have accounted for damages to library buildings in universities. One of the librarians said that *there is always delay from the works department whenever they are alerted of an impending disaster citing administrative protocol.....* which has affected library operation.

Technological factors were also identified as causes of disaster in the library such as *electricity and electrical sparks, power surges and faulty connections* were identified as the major cause fire outbreaks. In one of the libraries, it was reported that:

...there were wrong electrical connections that led to electrical sparks in the library that we noticed before we alerted the works department. The fire from the spark caused black stains on the wall of the building, cable and socket were damaged. We put out all light in the library from the control switch before the works and maintenance department arrived... (Librarian 3).

Other technological disasters reported were equipment failure and damage mostly from furniture breakdown, machine breakdown such as printers, and photocopiers.

Discussion

This study examined the types and causes of disasters in university libraries in North East Nigeria. The findings revealed that disasters experienced in these libraries include electrical faults, fire outbreaks, windstorms, roof leakages, and erosion. These findings indicate that disaster occurrences in academic libraries are largely linked to infrastructural vulnerabilities and environmental exposure.

The prevalence of electrical faults and fire incidents as major disaster types aligns with existing literature, which identifies faulty wiring and unstable power supply as leading causes of fire outbreaks in libraries, particularly in developing countries. For instance, Feather and Matthews (2003) emphasised that poor electrical installations and inadequate maintenance significantly increase fire risks in library environments. Similarly, Miller and Pellen (2008) noted that electrical failures and power-related issues are among the most common threats to library infrastructure and collections. The recurrence of these issues in North East Nigerian university libraries reflects broader systemic challenges associated with ageing infrastructure and inconsistent electricity supply.

Environmental factors such as windstorms, flooding, and roof leakages were also identified as significant contributors to disasters. These findings are consistent with studies that highlight the vulnerability of libraries in tropical regions to climatic conditions. Research has shown that heavy rainfall, high humidity, and extreme weather conditions accelerate the deterioration of library materials and increase the likelihood of structural damage International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC, 2019). In the Nigerian context, Owolabi and Ogundele (2022) similarly found that flooding and poor drainage systems pose persistent threats to academic institutions, including libraries.

A notable and unique finding of this study is the identification of soil expansion and erosion as causes of structural damage to library buildings. This reflects a geotechnical risk that is rarely highlighted in library disaster literature. The presence of cracks in library buildings due to land instability suggests that environmental hazards in the region extend beyond conventional factors such as rainfall and windstorms. This finding underscores the importance of incorporating geotechnical assessments into library planning and infrastructure development, particularly in erosion-prone areas.

Human-related factors, including negligence, poor maintenance practices, and delays in response from maintenance departments, were also identified as key causes of disasters. These findings support previous studies that attribute many library disasters to operational failures rather than purely natural causes. For example, George (1995) noted that lack of preparedness and poor adherence to safety procedures significantly increase disaster risks in libraries. Similarly, Okonkwo and Ede (2020) observed that administrative inefficiencies and weak enforcement of safety measures contribute to disaster occurrence in Nigerian academic institutions.

Technological factors such as equipment failure, power surges, and faulty electrical connections were also identified as major causes of disasters. This finding reflects the growing dependence of modern libraries on electrical and digital infrastructure, which introduces additional vulnerabilities. Studies have shown that inadequate technological infrastructure and lack of backup systems can lead to significant disruptions in library services and loss of digital resources (Olanrewaju et al., 2021). This study contributes to the literature by providing context-specific evidence from North East Nigeria, a region that has received limited scholarly attention in disaster management studies in academic libraries. The findings demonstrate that disasters in university libraries are not isolated events but the result of interconnected environmental, infrastructural, human, and technological factors. This emphasises the need for a comprehensive and integrated

approach to disaster management that addresses both physical and operational vulnerabilities within academic library environments.

Conclusion

This study examined the types and causes of disasters in university libraries in North East Nigeria. The findings revealed that disasters such as fire outbreaks, electrical faults, windstorms, roof leakages, and erosion have occurred across the libraries studied. These disasters were found to arise from a combination of environmental, human, and technological factors, including poor infrastructure, faulty electrical systems, inadequate maintenance practices, and institutional delays in responding to emerging risks. The study further established that disaster occurrences in university libraries are not isolated events but are closely linked to systemic vulnerabilities within the physical and operational environments of these institutions. The presence of unique environmental challenges, such as soil expansion and erosion affecting library buildings, highlights the need for context-specific approaches to disaster management in the region. Despite the valuable insights provided, the study is limited by its qualitative design and relatively small sample size of thirteen university librarians, which may restrict the generalisability of the findings. In addition, the study focused only on the types and causes of disasters without examining their impacts. Future research may adopt a mixed-methods approach and explore the long-term effects of disasters on library services and user access.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Increased funding for disaster prevention and recovery. The government, university management, and relevant stakeholders should allocate a dedicated budget for structural repairs and maintenance, procurement of modern disaster response tools (e.g., smoke detectors, water-resistant storage, fire suppression systems), and library staff training on disaster management.
2. Strengthening library infrastructure. Universities should conduct structural integrity assessments of library buildings and take necessary actions to fix electrical faults and faulty wiring to reduce fire risks, reinforce roofs and walls to withstand windstorms and flooding, and improve drainage systems to prevent water damage and erosion.
3. University libraries should conduct periodic risk assessments to identify vulnerabilities related to environmental, infrastructural, and technological factors.
4. Institutions located in erosion-prone or unstable areas should conduct geotechnical assessments and structural monitoring to prevent damage caused by soil expansion and land instability.

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